

Learning Strategies Employed by Undergraduate Students in Online Learning

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ABSTRACT

Academic institutions throughout the Philippines have switched from in-person education to online training during the COVID-19 pandemic. Students have employed a variety of learning strategies to cope with their online learning experiences, and others simply understand the concepts in the course materials that the instructors have provided. The study adopted the design theory of technology-based student-centered learning as initial foundation to explore the strategies of learning employed by the learners in online learning. In order to investigate the learning strategies used by students in online learning, the study mainly adopted the design theory of technology-based student-centered learning as its initial foundation. San Isidro College served as the research locale and the college student enrolled during the first semester of the academic year 2021-2022 served as the respondents of the study. The quantitative data employed the descriptive statistics and the qualitative data were treated thematically. The study revealed that the students effectively applied both cognitive and metacognitive and resource management strategies.

Subject Area

Online Learning; Learning Strategies

Keywords: *Online Learning, Learning Strategies, Cognitive and Metacognitive Strategies, Resource Management Strategies*

INTRODUCTION

During the COVID-19 pandemic academic institutions have shifted from face-to-face instruction to online instruction (Brooks, Grajek, Lang, 2020). Due to the abrupt shift of instruction, many students, even teachers, encountered problems with the implementation of online

learning. Some of the problems that were encountered were connection, technical know-how, finance, and even learning itself (Morin, 2020). The problems encountered by the students have affected their learning and some have even problems with understanding their materials due to the lack of explanation, understanding, background knowledge, and even lack of instruction (Venkataraman, 2020).

Articles of Avila and Genio (2020), Long (2019), and Wegner, Minnaert, and Strehkle (2013) suggested that using of learning strategies could help students learn better in an online setting. These strategies could differ from one student to another. According to Pintrich, Smith, Garcia, and McKeachie (1991), these learning strategies could be grouped into two categories. The first being the cognitive and metacognitive strategies that guide the student to manage the information provided to understand and process for a meaningful learning experience. And the second is the resource management strategies that helps students categorize and identify relevant materials that can used for learning.

During the online learning experience, students have resorted to varied learning strategies to cope and implement a few just to grasp the concepts of the instructional materials that were provided by the instructors (Avila and Genio, 2020). The researchers have observed that some students have stated that they were having problems with understanding their learning material. However, some instructors have suggested different learning methods that the students could implement to help them learn better and cope-up with their academic requirements.

The study identified the different cognitive and metacognitive strategies and resource management strategies used by the students during the academic year 2021-2022. Teachers' awareness of the strategies the students are capable of doing could help them develop learning materials that could enrich the students' repertoire of learning skills and experiences.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study adopts the design theory of technology-based student-centered learning (Hannafin and Land, 1997) as an initial foundation to explore the elements of an online student-centered learning environment. The study involves evaluating the students' motivation to learn online and gathering students' insights in learning through online modality.

Learning strategies are techniques of a set of skills that students employ to comprehend various learning and academic task (McComb, 2017). Students employ learning methods to improve the processes of attaining and retaining knowledge and academic concepts. The ultimate goal of these strategies is for learners to extract this material from memory and apply learned concepts (Yip, 2019).

The framework of the study as shown in Figure 1 illustrates the parsimonious embedded design. The independent variable are the students' strategies used to learn online where the two major strategies are embedded to quantitatively measure the students online learning strategies. The students experience along with the numerical data was used to assess the students online learning strategies.

Figure 1

Schematic diagram of the framework of the study

Students must employ learning strategies in order to develop practical application of concepts from education (Wegner, Minneart, and Strehkle, 2013). Pintrich, Smith, Garcia, and McKeachie (1991) listed two major strategies for learning, particularly: the *Cognitive and Metacognitive Strategies* which evaluates the students learning and development strategies like rehearsal of information, elaborating learned concepts through self-regulated learning, and organizing of notes and concepts. The second strategy is *Resource Management Strategy* which evaluates the students' ability to manage time and available resources to them and even innovate strategies to establish a conducive learning environment.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study examined the learning strategies employed by the undergraduate students in online learning at San Isidro College during the Academic Year 2021-2022. Specifically, it answered the following:

1. What are the learning strategies of the undergraduate students in terms of;
 - 1.1. cognitive and metacognitive strategies;
 - 1.1.1. rehearsal;
 - 1.1.2. elaboration;
 - 1.1.3. organization;
 - 1.1.4. critical thinking; and
 - 1.1.5. metacognitive self-regulation;
 - 1.2. resource management strategies;
 - 1.2.1. time and study environment;
 - 1.2.2. effort regulation;
 - 1.2.3. peer learning; and
 - 1.2.4. help seeking?
2. What are the students' experiences considering;
 - 2.1. cognitive and metacognitive strategies; and
 - 2.2. resource management strategies?

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study utilized the mixed method design employing the parsimonious embedded design from the result of the survey from the college students. San Isidro College (SIC) served as the research locale where the online instruction was employed. San Isidro College was founded by the late Fr. Joseph Reith, S.J. It is the only Catholic Institution of higher learning in the City of Malaybalay, and the oldest in the province of Bukidnon. The participants of the study were the college students enrolled for the Academic Year of 2021-2022. There were 733 students enrolled

during the first semester and the researchers gathered 269 random samples from the 9 different schools.

The major instrument adopted for the study is the questionnaire developed by Pintrich, Smith, Garcia, and McKeachie (1991) containing two (2) major strategies, namely; The *Cognitive and Metacognitive Strategies* with five (5) sub-strategies, particularly; the *Rehearsal* with four (4) statements assessing the students' ability to practice learned concepts, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.734. The second sub-strategy is *Elaboration* with six (6) statements assessing the students' ability to detail learned concepts, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.752. The third sub-strategy is *Organization* with four (4) statements that assess the students' strategy to organize information and categorize learned concepts, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.694. The fourth sub-strategy is *Critical Thinking* with five (5) statements that assess the students' ability to analyze information and identify important parts of the learned concepts, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.657. And the last sub-strategy is *Metacognitive Self-Regulation* with twelve (12) statements that assess the students' ability to think about their learning, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.828.

The second strategy is on *Resource Management Strategy* with four (4) sub-strategies, particularly: The *Time and Study Environment* with eight (8) statements that assess the student ability to manage their time and prepare themselves and their surroundings for learning, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.810. The second sub-strategy is *Effort Regulation* with four (4) statements that evaluates that student's ability to give effort to activities and requirements that is needed from the learners, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.730. The third sub-strategy is *Peer Learning* with three (3) statements that assess the students regulated learning along with their fellow students, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.654. The last sub-strategy is *Help Seeking* with four (4) statements that assess the students' ability to seek out for help from other learners for information exchange and content clarification, with a Cronbach of 0.744.

A 7-point Likert scale evaluates the students' strategies used in online learning. The questionnaire has an overall Cronbach alpha of 0.962. The questionnaire contains the students' learning strategies based on the two (2) learning strategies. The criteria used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
7	6.16 – 7.00	<i>Very Effective</i>
6	5.30 – 6.15	<i>Effective</i>
5	4.44 – 5.29	<i>Fairly Effective</i>
4	3.57 – 4.43	<i>Neither</i>
3	2.72 – 3.57	<i>Fairly Ineffective</i>
2	1.86 – 2.71	<i>Ineffective</i>
1	1.00 – 1.85	<i>Very Ineffective</i>

The questionnaire provided a space for narrative feedback from the students on their experience in applying the strategies for learning. The quantitative data was treated using independent t-test to compare the two strategies of learning and the ANOVA test to compare the sub-strategies of learning. The qualitative data was treated using the thematic analysis to categorize the learner's response into a common theme. The qualitative result was used to support the quantitative result.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Learning Strategies of Students in Online Learning

Table 1 presents the comparison of students cognitive and metacognitive strategy and resource management strategy. Additionally, Table 1 presents the mean score with qualitative interpretation in effectiveness of learning strategies. The table also presents the degree of satisfaction of the students.

Table 1
Comparison of the learning strategies of undergraduate students in online leaning

PARAMETER	MEAN	Q.D.	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Cognitive and Metacognitive Strategies	5.15	Effective	1.800	0.072
Resource Management Strategies	5.02	Effective		
OVERALL	5.10	Effective		

As presented in Table 1, the t-value for the two strategies is 1.800 with a p-value of 0.072. The result indicates that there is no significant difference between the two strategies used by the students. Both strategies are within the range that indicates effectiveness. Moreover, students' implementation of cognitive and metacognitive strategy is as effective as the student's implementation of resource management strategies. As shown in Table 1, the overall implementation of learning strategies is effective.

Learning strategy is varied and dependent on the learner. The learner would adjust if the strategy is difficult or would change strategies if it is ineffective. Additionally, learners who found effective strategies would either improve on the strategy they are using or would mix it with other strategies (Long, 2019; Yip, 2019). The result would suggest that the learners identified strategies that would suit them well and that could help them maximize their self-paced learning (Roces and Sierra, 2017). Online learning is not easy especially if the students does not know how to digest the materials and synthesize the contents (Avila and Genio, 2020). The varied strategy that the students applied, as shown in Table 1, are effective and shows that the students can regulate their thinking and manage themselves even if learning is not in schools.

Cognitive and Metacognitive Strategies

Table 2 presents the mean score and comparison of the sub-strategies under cognitive and metacognitive strategy. Additionally, Table 2 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation effectiveness of strategy to online learning concerning cognitive and metacognitive strategies and presents the degree of effectiveness of the students.

Table 2
Cognitive and metacognitive strategies of students in online learning

PARAMETER	MEAN	Q.D.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Organization	5.24 a	Effective	0.957	0.430
Elaboration	5.19 a	Effective		
Rehearsal	5.18 a	Effective		
Metacognitive Self-Regulation	5.12 a	Effective		
Critical Thinking	5.09 a	Effective		
OVERALL	5.15	Effective		

As shown in Table 1, the students find the strategies effective for both cognitive and metacognitive strategies. Moreover, as shown in Table 2, the learners are effective in all statements under the cognitive and metacognitive strategies. Furthermore, the f-value of the sub-categories is 0.957 with a p-value of 0.430 ($p > 0.05$), indicating that there is no significant difference between the sub-strategies. It follows that the student's implementation of the sub-strategies under cognitive and metacognitive strategies are the same.

Roces and Sierra (2017) support the result considering that students would naturally look for the most effective strategy without obstructing other aspects of learning. Hence, students would want to find the most effective strategy for learning that encompass all the sub-strategies. Moreover, considering each sub-strategy, Yip (2019) emphasizes that learners consider each aspect of the cognitive process and maximizes on those aspects to yield the best result for the learning endeavor.

Figure 2 displays the overview of the implementation of the students in cognitive and metacognitive strategies and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded: Learning Methods (63.57%), External Influence (25.28%), Internal Influence (7.43%), and the students that gave no response (3.72%). For every theme, sub-themes were also recorded. Through these responses, the researcher has a baseline data for students' implementation of their cognitive and metacognitive strategy.

Figure 2
Cognitive and metacognitive strategies implemented by learners

Learning Strategies Employed by Undergraduate Students in Online Learning

Frame 1 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students' implementation of cognitive and metacognitive strategies. Example of verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 1

Summary of the qualitative themes on the implementation of cognitive and metacognitive strategies of students

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	EXAMPLES
Learning Strategies	Familiarization	<i>"familiarizing the important things in my notes"</i>
	Outlining	<i>"... make a take note the important meaning"</i>
	Researching	<i>"...research about the topic"</i>
	Memorizing	<i>"...also memorize it not only by words but by its meaning."</i>
	Practicing	<i>"Create a problem and solve"</i>
	Reading	<i>"Reading the materials that teachers give"</i>
External Influence	Food/Beverage	<i>"I use snacks to motivate me to study..."</i>
	Multimedia	<i>"I want to listen to the music while I am studyinh" "Listen motivational video"</i>
	Location	<i>"Find a place that makes me comfortable..."</i>
	Time	<i>"I study at night so no one can disturb me."</i>
	People	<i>"i ask friend help on subject i dont understand"</i>
Internal Influence	Motivation	<i>"I motivate and push my self to study"</i>
	Spirituality	<i>"first I will pray so that i can understand and remember what im studying"</i>

NOTE: Response are copied verbatim

Theme 1: Learning Strategies. The first theme has six (6) sub-themes, namely, familiarization, outlining, researching, memorizing, practicing, and reading. The students have stated that they identified learning strategies that worked well for them in learning the content of the subject that they are currently taking. Employing learning strategies helped students cope with the requirements that is asked from them and the content that needs to be learned.

Learning strategies provide methods for students to adjust, cope, and maximize learning in an effective way (Donker, de Boer, Kostons, Dignath van Ewijk, and van der Werf, 2014; Yip, 2019). Students select the strategies that would help them learn the content of a subject in meaningful manner and that would maximize time and effort. Additionally, students apply varied strategies to improve their performance (Daouk, Bahous, and Bacha, 2016; Montero and Arizmendiarieta, 2017; Long, 2019).

Themes 2 and 3: External and Internal Influence. The second theme five (5) sub-themes, namely, food/beverage, multimedia, location, time, and people. The second theme has two (2) sub-themes, namely, motivation and spirituality. Both these themes express influence on the students' learning habits. The external factors that the student enumerated states that they require outside incentive or conditions to help them learn. Moreover, the internal factors stated by the learners claimed that they have inner drives to push them to learn or guides them in the learning process.

External factors have significant effects on the learning of the students. As stated by the students, they have different external motivator to help them learn like food and multimedia or

thrust them to learn properly like time and location (Zhang, 2022). Moreover, the study of Zaccone and Pedrini (2019) mentioned that internal factors have a strong correlation to the effectiveness of the students learning. Internal factors that the students have identified guide them to improve themselves and take full advantage of their learning (Ramli, Muljono, and Afendi, 2018; Long, 2019).

As revealed in Table 2, the students displayed effective application of all five (5) parameters under the cognitive and metacognitive strategies. The metacognitive self-regulation of the students plays an important role in the learning process of the student. As shown in Frame 1, students have applied meta-cognitive strategies to help them learn better and understand what they need in order to facilitate an effective learning session. Overall, the students showed effective application of cognitive and metacognitive strategies.

Resource Management Strategies

Table 3 presents the mean score and comparison of the sub-strategies under resource management strategy. Additionally, Table 3 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation effectiveness of strategy to online learning concerning resource management strategies and presents the degree of effectiveness of the students.

Table 3

Resource management strategies of students in online learning

PARAMETER	MEAN	S.D.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Time and Study Environment	5.21 a	Effective	14.168	0.000**
Help Seeking	5.06 ab	Effective		
Effort Regulation	4.83 bc	Effective		
Peer Learning	4.69 c	Effective		
OVERALL	5.02	Effective		

NOTE: ** - significant at 0.01

As shown in Table 1, the students are effective in their overall resource management strategies. Moreover, as shown in Table 3, the learners are effective in all statements under the resource management strategies. Furthermore, the *f*-value of the sub-categories is 14.168 with a *p*-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating that there is a significant difference between the sub-strategies. Additionally, Table 3 illustrates that *time and study environment* were most effective and *peer learning* have the lowest effectiveness rate.

The study of Barrot, Llenares, and del Rosario (2021) further supports the result. Their study stated that students, due to the shift of instruction and resort to different learning strategies. Additionally, student try to manage their time and resources in order to optimize their learning in the environment. Moreover, student would need to facilitate their own learning as some of them opted for modular instruction. Modular instruction pushes the student to manage themselves and divide their time accordingly to take up the coverage that they need to complete (Garcia, Falkner, and Vivian, 2020; Putri and Mahmudah, 2021).

Figure 3 displays the overview of the implementation of the students in resource management strategies and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded: Planning (91.82%), Problematic (3.72%), Does not manage (2.23%), and the students that gave no response (2.23%). For every theme, the sub-themes were also recorded. Through these responses, the

researchers obtained a baseline data for students’ implementation of their resource management strategy.

Figure 3
Resource management strategies implemented by learners

Frame 2 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students’ implementation of cognitive and metacognitive strategies. Example of verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 2
Summary of the qualitative themes on the implementation of resource management strategies of students

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	EXAMPLES
Planning	Scheduling	“I set may time that cannot conflict...”
	Task Management	“First is I do things which is have to do it right a way and think what should I do next.”
	Prioritizing	“prioritizing the most important things and start with the nearest deadline.”
	Time Management	“I manage my time to think...”
Problematic	Difficulty in Management	“Im struggling with management here at home”
	Overwhelmed	“mismanagement of my time due to overwhelmed activities”
Does Not Manage		“I don’t manage my time ...”

NOTE: Response are copied verbatim

Theme 1: Planning. The first theme has four (4) sub-themes, namely, scheduling, task management, prioritizing, and time management. Students mentioned that in order for them to manage their time and resources, they plan what to do. Student claimed that planning helps them in the best possible way to manage themselves and their learning.

A student's ability to plan out their activities will help them succeed in their learning endeavor, considering their time available to study, list of priority activities to be submitted, and available resources to help foster learning (Long, 2019; Yip, 2019). Planning the learning activities by the students require them to facilitate themselves in order to follow through and give priority to what needs to be done and submitted to the instructor. Student need to consider their time and their resources available in order to fully plan their activities (Avila and Genio, 2020; Putri and Mahmudah, 2021).

Themes 2 and **Theme 3: Problematic and Does Not Manage.** The second theme has two (2) sub-themes, namely difficulty in management and overwhelmed. Students have stated that they have problems in managing their time and resources and some have stated that they do not even manage their time and resources.

Learners come across problems regarding their time and resource management due to some constraint they have at home, from home responsibilities to work to connection. These factors of difficulty could affect the student learning processes and hinder their ability to plan out and schedule their academic activities (Putra, Liriwati, Tahrim, Syafrudin, and Aslan, 2020).

As revealed in Table 3, student have displayed effective application of all four (4) parameters under the resource management strategy. Among all parameters, the parameter on time and study environment has the most effective application for the students. The result can further be supplemented by Frame 2 under the theme on Planning, since students plot what they need to do and set schedules when to do their activities. Among the four (4) parameters, peer learning had the least effective application. This could be explained by student not knowing each other and could be timid when contacting other or conversing with their classmate (Ding and Yao, 2020).

SUMMARY

The strategy on cognitive and metacognitive learning revealed an effective utilization of all five (5) parameters. Moreover, there is no difference between the parameters and that the learners are able to consider all five (5) parameters when learning. The strategy on resource management revealed an effective utilization of all four (4) parameters. Moreover, there is a significant difference between the parameter where time and study environment have the highest effectiveness for the student while peer learning has the lowest effectiveness for the students.

Comparing the two strategies revealed that there is no difference between the two and both were effectively applied by the learners based from the result of the statistics. More research is needed on the learning strategies implemented by the students exploring the relationship between the online learning strategies employed.

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